

Project	GUTTA
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Deliverable title	Six-monthly progress report no2
Deliverable Responsible Partner	CMCC
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Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	2
2. Project progress	2
2.1 General achievements.....	2
2.2 Issues fixed or under processing.....	3
2.3 Status metrics	3
2.3.1 Financial	3
2.3.2 Technical	6
3. Conclusions.....	7

1. Executive Summary

This report documents the GUTTA project progress in fulfilment of its specific and communication objectives during the reporting period ranging from 2019-07-01 to 2019-12-31, also termed in the following RP2. Please note that full technical and financial information is declared on SIU platform and the present report just represents an overview of related contents.

It includes reference to project deliverables of this period as well as documentation of major unforeseen delays and achievements.

When not re-defined here, shortcuts refer to the public GUTTA Glossary, which can be found at www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3667198

2. Project progress

The report is organized into General achievements (Sect.2.1), unforeseen Issues (Sect.2.2), and a summary of project status by means of key metrics (Sect.2.3).

2.1 General achievements

CMCC as LP of GUTTA has steered the administrative and technical implementation of the project.

Administrative milestone achievements were:

- Sept. 30: submission of the RP1 report
- Nov.18: successful resubmission of the RP1 report after PO's and PPs review
- Nov.29: AdSP staff for GUTTA, including a new project manager, was nominated

Technical milestone achievements were:

- Oct.1-2: SC meeting #1 in Zagreb
- Dec.20: Submission to the LP of 9 of the 13 Deliverable documents due in RP2 (see Tab.1 in this report)

Also, concerning the Communication, after some technical problems suffered in the initial months of the project, the Institutional webpage <https://www.italy-croatia.eu/web/gutta> was finally put online by the MA and first updates were provided by the LP.

A teleconference was organized on Sept. 6 for informing about implementation status and next challenges of the project. Furthermore, remote bilateral meetings with selected PPs occurred throughout RP2.

2.2 Issues fixed or under processing

The main issue is underspending due to the fact that, expenditures were regularly reported by CMCC, CSA and UniZd, but MMPI and AdSP did not report any expenditures in either RP2 or in RP1.

Another issue is that LP had to replace some PP in finalizing the following deliverables:

- 2.1.3 Report with a strategy for communication activities (PP in charge originally was AdSP)
- 3.1.2 Report on CB maritime traffic data (PP in charge originally was MMPI)
- 3.2.2 Database of ferry propulsion and performance data (PP in charge: UniZd)

For D.2.1.3, AdSP staff was not completely assigned and their administrative activities for project start up were not complete. Thus, LP's communication office replaced AdSP, in order to deliver the Communication strategy D.2.1.3 in due time for fulfilling the project dissemination needs.

For D.3.1.2, MMPI declared not to have the technical expertise for analyzing the maritime traffic data they provided. Thus, given that the other PPs were not available either, this task has been taken under direct responsibility of the LP.

For D. 3.2.2, the work on the parametrization of vessel CO₂ emissions in terms of environmental state variables (due by D.4.1.1) starting from UniZd simulator's data was performed by CMCC and anticipated with respect to the D.4.1.1 deadline, for facilitating the coding developments for the eco-routes tool.

The rest of the activities proceeded as planned.

2.3 Status metrics

The status of the project is monitored through both financial and technical implementation data, as reported in the following two subsections.

2.3.1 Financial

The financial absorption, inclusive of implementation gaps, both at WP and activity level, is summarized in Fig.1-4. The title of activities are provided in Tab.1.

Figure 1 WP1 implementation status at the end of RP2. Blue is the cumulative implemented fraction; orange is the gap fraction, grey is the remainder till project's end. Negative values in the gap fraction indicate overspending.

Figure 2 Like Fig.1 but for WP2.

Figure 3 Like Fig.1 but for WP3.

Figure 4 Like Fig.1 but for WP4.

Table 1 Activities executed in RP2.

A. number	Activity title
1.1	Start-up activities
1.2	Day-to-day project management, coordination and internal communication
1.3	Steering and monitoring of the project implementation
1.4	Financial management
2.1	Start-up activities
2.2	External communication
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders
3.1	Input data collection
3.2	Initial data analysis and planning
4.1	Emissions and routing models
4.2	MRV - data collection guidance
4.3	Preliminaries for new CB maritime routes
4.4	Eco-routes DSS

The overall implementation rate is defined as the actual cumulative absorption compared to the planned absorption. At the end of RP2, this indicator reads 72.6%. The underspending is mainly due to insufficient absorption in the staff budget line of WP3, due to two PPs (MMPI and AdSP) not reporting any expenses so far.

More information on the breakdown of the budget absorption can be found in the financial report of RP2, corresponding to deliverable D.1.4.2.

2.3.2 Technical

The technical advancement is monitored through the status of the Deliverables of RP2 in Tab.2.

Table 2 Status of implementation of deliverables of the present period completed.

	D. number	D. title	Month due	PP in charge	D. status	notes
1	1.3.1	SC meeting report no1	10	CMCC	finalized	
2	1.2.2	6-monthly progress report no2	12	CMCC	finalized, after RP2 end	
3	1.4.2	6-monthly financial report no2	12	CMCC	finalized, after RP2 end	
4	2.1.2	Stakeholders database	08	AdSP	finalized	
5	2.1.3	Report with a strategy for communication activities	08	AdSP	finalized	Lead by CMCC
4	2.2.1.	Project brochures	08	UniZd	finalized	
7	3.1.1	Report on vessel fuel and CO2 emission data availability	09	CSA	finalized	
8	3.1.2	Report on CB maritime traffic data	09	MMPI	Finalized by LP after RP2 end	Lead by CMCC
9	3.1.3	Collection of raw data of vessel propulsion and performance	09	UniZd	finalized	
10	3.1.4	Catalogue of forecast fields	09	CMCC	finalized	
11	3.2.1	Report on implementation challenges for MRV	12	CSA	finalized	
12	3.2.2	Harmonized and queryable database of ferry propulsion and performance data	12	UniZd	finalized, after RP2 end	Contribution by CMCC
13	3.2.3	Report on the literature survey of optimization algorithms	12	CMCC	finalized	

All RP2 deliverables (they are 13) are complete and ready to be submitted to the SIU system.

3. Conclusions

The implementation of GUTTA project activities is monitored by the present report.

The overall financial absorption is about 73% of planned, with an underspending share due to two PPs not reporting any expenses so far. This affected the realization of the project deliverables, with LP taking direct responsibility over two of them (cf. Tab.2), in order to fulfil GUTTA's commitment and ensure advancement towards the project Specific Objectives.

Some deliverables were finalized only after RP2's end but still in time for submission to the SIU system by end March 2020.